

Emergence of Sixth Schedule in the Constitution of India

Lalbiakzami Ralte¹ & Prof. Jangkhongam Doungel²

Abstract: This paper examines the colonial policies that were enforced in the areas now governed under the Sixth Schedule prior to India's independence. It will discuss in detail how these policies shaped the administration and socio-political conditions of tribal regions, laying the groundwork for later constitutional safeguards. Further, the paper will analyse the steps undertaken by the Constituent Assembly in addressing the unique concerns of tribal communities, which eventually culminated in the framing of the Sixth Schedule of the Indian Constitution. Attention will also be given to the debates within the Constituent Assembly, highlighting the discussions, disagreements, and consensus-building that influenced the decision to provide a special constitutional framework for tribal areas.

Key words: Sixth Schedule, Constituent Assembly, Constitution, Committee, Government

Introduction

The framers of the Constitution recognize the diversity of the people and the need for special arrangement for the administration of certain regions. As a result of the adoption of proposal made by the Bordoloi sub-committee in the Constituent Assembly of India, the provision for enabling the tribals with constitutional autonomy was incorporated in the constitution of India. It was inserted in Articles 244 (2) and 275 (1) and was put in the Sixth Schedule of the constitution. The Sixth Schedule to the Constitution of India is therefore, one such arrangement made for the administration of tribal areas in Northeast India ensuring that tribal communities could preserve their distinct customs, rights, traditions etc., and to provide them with autonomy in governance while remaining part of the Indian Union.

Various Colonial Policies Imposed by the British Government Before Independence:

The British after gaining control over the tribals of the hill areas of Assam realized that the laws, regulations and rules which were enforced in the plains might not be applicable in the hill territories. Therefore, some legislations were enforced for preservation and protection of the custom, culture, tradition and land of the

¹ PhD Scholar, Department of Political Science, Mizoram University

² Professor, Department of Political Science, Mizoram University

tribal people of the hill areas. Those legislations which were enforced exclusively for tribal people of the hill territories before independence were as below:

1) Regulation X of 1822:

The Regulation X of 1822 was the first regulation enforced by the British Indian Government for administering of hill tribes in the eastern Frontier Region of Bengal. It laid down the foundation for the pattern of administration of the tribal areas of Northeast India which should be used in governance by the British administration. A beginning was made of a new form of administration popularly known as the Non-regulated System.

2) Garo Hills Act, 1869:

The Garo Hills Act of 1869 was enacted to remove Garo Hills from the jurisdiction of civil, criminal and revenue courts and offices established under the general regulations and acts. It also laid down that the Garo Hills bounded by Goalpara on the north and west, Mymensingh on the south as defined by the Revenue Survey and the Khasi Hills in the east shall be removed from the jurisdiction of the Courts of Civil and Criminal Jurisdiction and from the control of offices of revenue constituted by the Regulation of Bengal Code.

3) Bengal Eastern Frontier Regulation, 1873:

The Bengal Eastern Frontier Regulation, 1873 was made under the Government of India Act 1870. Popularly known as the Inner Line Regulation (ILR), it was the first law promulgated concerning the hill tribes for peace and good governance of eastern frontier areas of Bengal of which Assam was a part of it at that time. Subsequently Inner Line Regulation (ILR) or Inner Line Permit (ILP) was enforced in Kamarup, Darang, Nowgong, Sibsagar, Lakhimpur, Garo Hills, Khasi and Jaintia Hills, Naga Hills and Chittagong Hill Tract with effect from August 27, 1873.

Inner line regulation or Inner Line Permit ceased to function in some hill district namely Garo Hills, Khasi Hills, Jaintia Hills, Mikir Hills and North Cachar Hills though they were in the original notification. The Inner Line Regulation continued only in three hill districts, namely, North East Frontier Agency (NEFA) which later came to be known as Arunachal Pradesh, Lushai hills later known as Mizoram and Naga Hills later known as Nagaland.

4) Scheduled District Act, 1874:

On 6th February, 1874, Assam was put under a Chief Commissioner by taking away its management from the Lieutenant Governor of Bengal. In April of the same year, the Scheduled District Act, 1874 was enacted and all the tribal territories in the entire chief Commissioner province of Assam were declared as Scheduled District. The necessity for this Act was felt to remove the uncertainty that had existed regarding the actual operation of numbers of laws in various parts of the British India. The uncertainty related to the local enforceability of the enactments and even with regards to their being in operation or not. This confusion was sought to be removed by the Scheduled District Act, 1874.

5) Chin Hills Regulation, 1896:

The Chin Hills Regulation, 1896 was enforced in all territories of the Chin ethnic group. Chin signifies conglomerate group of people who are related by blood and who are traced to a common ancestor. As a result of subjugation of Chin Hills and Lushai Hills in the Chin-Lushai Expedition of 1889-1890 and annexation in the British Empire, the Chin Hills Regulation, 1896 was enforced in both Chin Hills and Lushai Hills and to other inhabited territories of the Chin or Zo ethnic group if the authority desired. Besides the Chin people, the Chin Hills Regulation of 1896 was also enforced upon Naga Hills, North East Frontier Tracts and other hill districts where the governing authority found it to be convenient. It was a regulation which was prepared and drafted in line with the Inner Line Regulation of 1873, so it could be described as a modified form of the Inner Line Regulation of 1873.

6) Government of India Act, 1919:

The Governor General in Council under sub-section (2) was mandated to declare any territory in British India as "Backward Tract" where the specific provisions of the Act may apply. In exercise of the powers as conferred in sub-section (2) of section 52A of the Act, the Governor General declared the following territories in the province of Assam as "Backward Tract". The Governor General in Council also authorized the Governor in Council of Assam to direct any of the Act of the Provincial Legislature of Assam whether it should or should not apply to the said territories or to any part thereof. The Backward Tracts were Garo Hills District, the British portion of Khasi-Jaintia Hills other than Shillong Municipality and Cantonment, the Mikir Hills in Nowgong and Sibsagar district, the North Cachar Hills in Cachar District, the Naga Hill District, the Lushai Hills District, the Sadiya Frontier Tract, the Balipara Frontier Tract and the Lakhimpur Frontier Tract.

The provision of the Act signify that any Act of the Legislature of Assam shall not be enforced in the Backward Tracts and Governor in Council had wide power in this regard. The Backward Tract were generally excluded from reform and normal administration and they were looked after with special laws under strict supervision of the Governor. Section 52A (2) also specified that absolute discretion was vested upon the Governor but provincial legislature had no much role in the Scheduled Districts.

7) Government of India Act, 1935:

The Government of India Act, 1930 can be described as the Constitution of India during British colonial rule and it was enacted by the British Parliament. This Act mentioned about 'tribal areas' which was defined in section 311(1) as "areas along the frontier of India or in Baluchistan which are not part of India or Burma or of any Indian State or of any foreign state". The powers exercisable over these areas were described as arising out of treaty, grant, usage, sufferance, or otherwise; and the Act enabled the Governor General to exercise powers in these areas acting in his discretion and therefore, outside the areas of the responsibility of the Ministry

The Government of India Act, 1935 gave up the terminology of the 'backward tract' and instead described it as 'excluded areas' or 'partially excluded areas. Excluded areas means backward most tribal areas which were under the direct rule of the Governor and districts which were categorized as excluded areas had no representation in the provincial legislature. Provincial Legislature also could not legislate any subjects in the Excluded Areas and the Excluded Areas were under direct rule of the Governor through the Superintendent od Deputy Commissioner of the district. Meanwhile, district which were categorized as Partially Excluded Areas were under the partial jurisdiction of the Provincial Government and they also had representation in the provincial legislature. However, the law enacted by the Provincial Legislature could not be enforced in the Partially Excluded Area without the approval of the Governor. Moreover, the Governor could use his discretionary power without consulting the Provincial Government in the Partially Excluded area. It should be noted that even with regard to the Partially Excluded Areas, the Provincial Government and Provincial Legislature did not have free hand of governance but steps could only be taken up in limited areas only with the approval of the Assam.

Incorporation Of Sixth Schedule in the Constitution of India

At the dawn of independence great care had been made by the Constituent Assembly on the questions of providing a suitable constitutional set-up for the tribal areas of Northeast India. In 1946, the Cabinet Commission comprising of three British Cabinet Ministers under the leadership of Sir Stafford Cripps came

to India. They were sent by the British Government to do the ground work for transfer of power from the British Government to Indian leadership, with the aim of preserving India's unity and granting its independence. The Mission suggested that an Advisory Committee on the Rights of the Citizens, Minorities and Tribal and Excluded Areas should be immediately formed by the Constituent Assembly to study and analyze upon the rights and privileges of tribal in Excluded and Partially Excluded Areas of Assam and other parts of India. Sir Stafford Cripps further said that this should be pursued without delay so as to facilitate the downtrodden section with constitutional rights.

The Constituent Assembly therefore set up an Advisory Committee in terms of the Cabinet Mission statement on 24th February 1947, under the Chairmanship of Sardar Vallabhai Patel. As responsibilities of the Advisory Committee were so vast and coverage area was so extensive, the Advisory Committee constituted three sub-committee which would analyze and study specific area. The three sub-committees were:

1. North East Frontier (Assam) Tribal and Excluded Area Sub-Committee.
2. North West Frontier Baluchistan Tribal and Excluded Area Sub-Committee.
3. Excluded and Partially Excluded Area (Other than Assam) Sub-Committee.

Gopinath Bordoloi was appointed as Chairman of the North East Frontier (Assam) Tribal and Excluded Area Sub-Committee, as such, the Sub-Committee came to be known popularly as Bordoloi Sub-Committee. Other members of the Sub-Committee were –

1. Rev JJM Nichols Roy,
2. Rup Nath Brahma,
3. Jaipur Singh,
4. A.V. Thakkar and
5. Mayang Nokcha, who was later replaced by Aliba Imti.

The Bordoloi Sub-Committee which comprised of Rup Nath Brahma, A.V. Thakker, Rev JJM Nichols Roy and B.N Rao, Constitutional Adviser to the Constituent Assembly of India visited Aizawl in April 1947. Besides visiting the Lushai Hills, the Bordoloi Sub-Committee also extensively toured the North Cachar Sub-Division, Mikir Hills and Naga Hills District but could not visit Garo Hills and Jowai area of Khasi Hills due to bad weather and communication problem. However, leader from Garo Hills met the Sub-Committee members in Gauhati and appraised them about their desire and expectation for Constitutional autonomy under the new Constitution of India. The Sub-Committee deliberated facts and analyzed ideas

and figures which they collected from its extensive tours and prepared report for inclusion in the Constitution. A report was submitted to Vallabhai Patel, who was the Chairman of Advisory Committee on Fundamental Rights etc. on 28th July, 1947. The report dealt with the various aspects relating to administration of the tribal areas. The report also recommended establishment of District Council and Regional Council for tribal areas of the then undivided Assam. Advisory Committee discussed the matter on 7th December, 1947 and 24th February, 1948 and suggested only two amendments while forwarding the report to the President of the Constituent Assembly on 4th March 1948. The Sixth Schedule was added to the Indian Constitution on 7th September, 1949.

Constituent Assembly Debates

There was animated discussion in the Constituent Assembly on the Bordoloi Sub-Committee Report. Different opinion was made by members in the Constituent Assembly when the matter was debated. Brajeshwar Prasad of Bihar expressed his desire for President to administer the area and not Provincial Government or Governor. In other words, areas under this provision should be brought within the central jurisdiction. On the other hand, against the previous opinion stated, two members from Assam, Kuladhar Chaliha and Rohini Kumar Chaudhuri, on several occasion in the debate had made it known that they wanted State Legislature and Provincial Government to have greater voice than what was originally proposed by the drafting committee.

The view of the then Chief Minister of Assam, Gopinath Bordoloi were given weight in the debate not only because he was the Chairman of the Sub-Committee but because he was known to be very kind and sympathetic to the hill people according to Rev JJM Nicholas Roy. Bordoloi explained to the Constituent Assembly the background in which the draft had been prepared. He also mentioned the various problems faced by these areas which were entirely isolated from the plain. According to Bordoloi, he found out that the ideas of isolation and separation was already instilled in the minds of people of the area when the survey was done by the Sub-Committee. The Sub-Committee therefore was confronted with the question whether for the purpose of integration “methods of force, the methods of use of Assam Rifles and the military forces, should be used, or a method should be used in which the willing cooperation of these people can be obtained for the purpose of governing these areas”.

According to Rev JJM Nichols Roy, the measure of self-government would make the tribals feel that the whole of India is sympathetic with them and nothing is going to be forced to them to destroy their feelings and culture. He reminded that to keep the frontier area safe, these people must be kept in a satisfied

condition. If force were to be used on them, more harm would be done as no advancement can come through force.

Dr B.R Ambedkar, Chairman of the Drafting Committee of the Constitution opined that the tribal people of Assam differed from tribals of other areas as the latter were more or less Hinduised, more or less assimilated with the civilization and culture of the majority of the people whereas for the former their roots were still in their own civilization and culture. He felt that the position of the tribals of Assam was somewhat similar to that of the Native Americans in the United States who are Republic by themselves in that country, and were regarded as a separate and independent people. He agreed that Regional and District Councils have been created to some extent on the lines which was adopted by the United States for the purpose of the Native Americans.

After much heated and long debate between the members, and after draft provisions underwent many amendments, the Sixth Schedule finally emerged and found place in the Constitution along with Articles 244(2) and 275(1). Article 244(2) in the original Constitution states the applicability of provisions of the Sixth Schedule in Tribal Areas of Assam but after many amendments was made in the Constitution. Article 244(2) now states about the application of the provisions of the Sixth Schedule in tribal areas of Assam, Meghalaya, Tripura and Mizoram. Whereas Article 275(1) state about the release of fund from the Consolidated Fund of India as grant-in-aid to tribal areas through the State Government.³

Conclusion

The emergence of the Sixth Schedule to the Constitution of India was the outcome of a careful historical and political process that sought to balance the imperatives of national integration with the preservation of tribal identity and autonomy. Rooted in the colonial legacy of excluded and partially excluded areas, and shaped by the recommendations of the Bordoloi Sub-Committee during the Constituent Assembly debates, the Sixth Schedule represented a conscious constitutional invention to address the aspirations of the North-Eastern tribal communities.

References

- DOUNGEL, Jangkhongam. *Constitutional Safeguards of the Indigenous People – A comparative Analysis of the Native Americans in the Constitution of the United States of America and Tribal*

³ Hansaria, Vijay. (2016). Justice B.L Hansaria's, Sixth Schedule to the Constitution. Haryana: LexisNexis (A division of RELX India Pvt Ltd). p-8-15

Under the Provision of the Sixth Schedule to the Constitution of India. Fullbright Nehru Academic and Professional Excellence Fellowship Programme 2020-2021, Unpublished.

- DOUNGEL, Jangkhongam. *Autonomous District Councils- A study of the implications of the Sixth Schedule in Mizoram, Dimension and Perspective: Society, Economy and Polity*, edited by J.K. Patnaik. (2008). New Delhi: Concept Publishing Company
- HANSARIA, Vijay. (2016). *Justice B.L Hansaria's, Sixth Schedule to the Constitution*. Haryana: LexisNexis (A division of RELX India Pvt Ltd).
- P.M. Bakshi. (2006). *The Constitution of India*. Delhi: Universal law Publishing Co. Pvt. Ltd.
- V. Venkata Rao, H.Thansanga & Niru Hazarika. (1987). *A Century of Government and Politics in Northeast India*. New Delhi: S. Chand Company (Pvt) Ltd.

Citation in APA 7th Edition:

Publisher's Note: *The views and opinions expressed in this article are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official policy or position of the publisher or editorial board. The publisher assumes no responsibility for any consequences arising from the use of information contained herein.*